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**ELECTRIC VEHICLES IN LOGISTIC OPERATIONS AND IMPACT ON
ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY**

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Abstract:

The goal of fully or partially electrifying their car fleets has already been proclaimed by a number of western nations. Both the logistics and transportation sectors stand to benefit greatly from the electrification of these processes. In modern economy logistical operations play a major role in driving both monetary and social development. Developing country like India, there has been recent interest from many logistic sectors in exploring the possibility of using electric vehicles (EVs) for logistical purposes. Therefore, it is crucial to get the opinion of logistic workers who have felt the effects of EVs before adopting them on a big scale in enterprises. Because of this, it is essential to investigate the perspectives of logisticians about EVs in the workplace. The purpose of this research is to examine logisticians' (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) perspectives on the sustainability effects of using electric vehicles (EVs) in logistic operations. Qualitative and quantitative methodologies are both used in this examination.

Logistic workers in the manufacturing sectors in Mysore, Karnataka, were surveyed using structured and objective questionnaires. Data analysis and interpretation were carried out using descriptive statistics, percentage technique, and t-test. As the results showed, using EVs in logistic operations has a major effect on logistic cost and also has a major effect on environmental sustainability. Consequently, there are several advantages to incorporating EVs into logistic operations that manufacturing concerns may reap. These include reduced logistic costs, more environmentally friendly operations, the possibility of receiving government subsidies, low carbon emissions, and overall benefits to environmental sustainability.

Keywords:

Electric vehicles, Environmental sustainability, Logistic cost, Logistic operations

1. Introduction:

On a global scale, logistical operations play an essential role and are a major driver of societal and economic development. Consistent expansion and significant influence on GDP are the reasons for the logistic sector's prominence. The global effect is more than the GDP of all nations combined due to its severity (Aronson & Huge Broden, 2006). Using "Electric Vehicles" is a crucial strategy for accomplishing a number of goals, including reduction of the negative influence on raw material transportation, enhancing logistical operations, reducing costs, and attaining environmental sustainability (Pernestal et al, 2020). According to Ao Dos Santos et al. (2014) and Dias D. (2022), the term "environmental sustainability" refers to an approach to business that seeks a middle ground between the needs of the earth, its inhabitants (the workers), and the bottom line. The mainway to achieve this equilibrium is by encouraging the use of electric vehicles (EVs) or alternative fuel vehicles.

Transportation of freight play vital role in economic development, but it is also harmful for the human health and nature. With concern of environment the business houses have started paying more attention on negative externalities of their operations companies should take precautions to reduce the likelihood of accidents involving their big commercial logistic trucks and the damage they cause harm to the employees during operations and impact of emission of carbon gases on health of employees (Abhishek et al, 2023) Profit is the main motto of the organization. The cost of logistic operation should be minimized and profit must be maximized. These EVs help the business concern

to reduce the cost which includes transportation cost, maintenance cost and other logistic costs. Further, adoption of these alternative fuel vehicles on the job helps them to claim subsidies to reduce acquisition cost from government, depreciation gains and other benefits. (Aktaretal,2021);Davis etal,2013)

Preserving natural environment on the planet earth is the fundamental duty of all the citizen. Using the EVs in logistic operations positively impact on reducing the carbon footprint and conserving the natural resources (Anget et al,2016). This balancing act will help to protect natural resources and conserve environment for future generation. Several green initiatives, including electric vehicles, a green supply chain, green marketing, and many more, should be implemented by a corporation in order to achieve economic balance. But they must plan a sustainable supply chain that incorporates several methods, such as environmentally friendly manufacturing, alternative fuel cars, trucks for delivery, etc. (Barratt and Oke, 2007).

In order to have fewer negative impact on nature, environmentally sensitive logistic policy requires changing in transportation schemes and switching over to sustainable distribution network (Lin et al, 2014). This made a way to have increase in environmental and social awareness regarding green initiatives at manufacturing and other business concern. The electric vehicles are now considered a serious alternative to conventional combustion vehicles in many fields. EVs has no CO₂ emission and produce only minimal noise. In order to improve this the government has started providing the required infrastructure to further boost electrification trend (Goese and Schneides,2015). In this research, we examine the effects of electric vehicles on logistical costs and environmental sustainability as they pertain to logistics operations. The other sections of the article are structured as follows: literature review, research questions and objectives, methods, results and discussions, conclusions, limitations, and scope for future research.

2. Earlier Studies and Literature Gap:

The present study focuses on existing literature on usage of EVs in business, logistic and transportation by considering the perception of logistic operation workers (Inventory manager, Warehouse manager, Logistic network manager), to identify the research gap.

Logistics is an important element of each and every business organization and also in terms of cost, it significantly contributes to the logistic cost and finally to the business cost as well along with the cost of goods sold (Balloue,1997; Pelletier et al, 2014). The transportation of goods across the nation is becoming more along with the emission of carbon at increasing rate (Napolietal,2021).

In the next couple of decades the transportation of freights are emitting around 12000 million tones of carbon (Dias,2022). This fact made a way for environment friendly approach to logistic and transportation activities. There is a lot of interest in finding ways to reduce the impact of logistics and transportation on the environment as they are major contributors to CO₂ emissions (Korzhenevych et al., 2016). The logistic sector has become largest contributor to emission of greenhouse gases (Juan et al,2016). To overcome emission of harmful greenhouse gases, reduce energy consumption and to preserve the natural environment, the usage of electric vehicles is needed (Sen 2009; Struben et al, 2007). The business concern must take positive steps to reduce emission cost and attempting to find a trade off between economic and environmental goals.

Mainly logistics and transportation sectors made positive remark towards minimization of emission cost and contributing to achieve environmental sustainability (Juan et al,2016). This can build the base for usage of alternative fuel vehicles or EVs in logistic operations. Yet, there is a lack of proper infrastructure in Western nations that may facilitate the widespread adoption of alternative fuel vehicles, such as electric automobiles. Public charging stations and service centers are essential infrastructural elements for electric vehicle usage. Luthra et al, 2022, observed that the proper support has to be given by the Government of India for improvement in use of EVs through different schemes that can cause fall in usage of petrol, reduction of overall cost and subsidies for acquisition of EVs and many more.

It is imperative that companies strive to include EVs into their logistical processes. Some of the factors that push businesses to become more environmentally conscious include government mandates and consumer demands (Preuss, 2002). Concerning issues pertaining to the decrease of detrimental effects on the environment and total logistical expenditure, there have been systemic shifts in logistical

operations. The research went on to say that improved health, more job prospects, a cleaner environment, and quicker economic development are all outcomes of businesses using EVs for logistics. Environmental sustainability is the important aspect which requires more research efforts. Adopting EVs in logistic operations requires technological advancement. The import of fossil fuel can be minimized by the usage of alternative fuel vehicles. The business organization would certainly gain advantage in minimizing overall business cost and maximizes productivity by adopting EVs in their business concern.(Abhisheketal,2023).

A few number of studies have looked at the use of EVs in logistic operations as a means to long-term environmental sustainability, according to the reviewed literature. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to examine how logistic workers (such as warehouse managers, inventory managers, and logistic network managers) in Mysore city's industrial sectors see the role of electric vehicles (EVs) in logistic operations and their effect on ecological sustainability.

3. Research Questions:

The following research questions were formulated by the study in light of the literature gap:

- a. What are the cost and benefits of using EVs in logistic operations?
- b. What is logistic workers (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) perception regarding impact of EVs on logistic operations?
- c. How does usage of EVs impact on environmental sustainability?

4. Research Objectives:

The study formulated the following three research objective using research questions.

- a. To conceptually assess the cost and benefits of using electric vehicles in logistic operations.
- b. Examine how logistic workers (such as warehouse managers, inventory managers, and logistic network managers) see the effects of electric vehicles on logistic operations
- c. To evaluate the usage of EVs impact of environmental sustainability

5. Hypothesis:

The following hypotheses were generated to accomplish the aims of the study:

1. H₀:The usage of EVs in logistic operations are not minimizing the logistic cost
2. H₀:The EVs in logistic operations are not significantly contributing to environmental sustainability.

6. Data Collection and Methodology:

Both primary and secondary sources of information were used to provide the empirical basis of this investigation. The logistic workers (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, and Logistic network managers) from the manufacturing companies in Mysore city are surveyed using a standardized questionnaire which is one of the quantitative approach and also focused group discussion was conducted which is one of the qualitative approach to get primary data. The secondary source of information are collected from published sources such as research articles, reports from governments and newspapers. The secondary sources were used to write the literature and develop the conceptual frame work. The convenience sampling approach was used to pick managers for the data collection. The following table displays the information of the responders.

TableNo.1 Respondents details

SI No	Respondents	No. of questionnaires Distributed	No. of responses collected	The response rate in percentage
1	Inventory managers	16	13	81%
2	Warehouse managers	14	13	93%
3	Logistic network mangers	18	11	61%
Total		48	37	77%

Source: Author Compiled

The logistic workers (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) are identified in industries of Mysore city such as Triveni Engineering and Industries ltd, Millenmum

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Chemi Pharma ltd, Hindustan Spring Manufacturing Co, Jagath Industry, Triphase Technologies Pvt Ltd, Motherland Food Specialties Pvt Ltd, Prem Industires, Mahishi Precision, following table shows the classification of respondents' based on actual data collected through survey.

Table No.2: Respondents' Segmentation of logistic workers (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) of different manufacturing industries of Mysore City.

SI No.	Manufacturing Co. selected for study	Inventory Managers	Warehouse Managers	Logistic Network Managers	Total
1	Triveni Engineering And Industries ltd	02	02	01	05
2	Millenmium Chemi Pharmaltd	02	02	01	05
3	Hindustan Spring Manufacturing Co	01	01	01	03
4	Jagath Industry	01	02	02	05
5	Triphase Technologies Pvt Ltd	01	01	02	04
6	Motherland Food Specialties Pvt Ltd	02	01	02	05
7	Prem Industires	02	02	01	05
8	Mahishi Precision	02	02	01	05
Total		13	13	11	37

Source: Primary data

7. Results and Discussions:

In this part of the article, the researcher has examined the findings from the main data and explain how they support or contradict the study's premise. The descriptive statistics and t-test has been used to explain the perception of logistic workers on usage of EVs in logistic operations and impact on logistic cost and environmental sustainability.

7.1 Perception of logistic workers on usage of EVs in logistic operations and impact on logistic cost The logistic workers who are on the job are having experience of the tools and machinery in the manufacturing industries. If the industries are taking positive steps towards adopting new technology for the manufacturing process such as movement of raw materials, delivery of goods and so on, they have to take the opinion of workers for implementing it, because they are the primary observers and experienced personnel. Introducing EVs in these operations is one such inducement. Hence the perception of logistic workers helps as valid input for the present research. This sections of paper runs through descriptive analysis regarding perception of logistic workers on usage of EVs in logistic operations and impact on logistic cost.

Table No.3 Results of one sample T-test at 5% significance level in regarding perception of logistic workers (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) on the usage of EVs in logistic operations and impact on logistic cost.

Perception variable regarding the usage of EVs in Logistic operations	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	sig
1.The use of EVs minimizes overall movement of products and people and also logistic cost.	37	3.916	1.105	4.977	0.00
2.Operating and maintaince cost of EVs are Less than other vehicles.	37	4.527	0.996	8.170	0.00
3.Subsidies provided by government reduces Overall logistic cost.	37	4.427	0.810	10.903	0.00
4.The acquisition cost of EVs is high and Repairs and maintaince is less.	37	3.972	0.877	6.645	0.00

5.The use of EVs promote eco friendly logistic operations.	37	4.527	0.624	10.442	0.00
6.The use of EVs `has positive impact onLogistic operations.	37	4.111	1.347	4.947	0.00
7.Depreciation benefits can be gained	37	4.833	0.378	29.103	0.00
8.Huge investment on logistic operation can beReduced by introducing EVs.	37	4.694	0.624	16.286	0.00
9.Subsidies provided by government on use of EVs positively impact on logistic operationcost.	37	4.417	1.180	7.620	0.01

Source: Primary data

The findings of a one-sample T-test at the 5% significance level are shown in Table No. 3 in regarding perception of logistic workers (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) on the usage of EVs in logistic operations and impact on logistic cost, which indicates all variable shows p-value less than 0.05. The logistic workers agree that using EVs minimizes overall logistic cost to the organization and minimizes movement of products and people (M=3.91) with the use of EVs encouraging environmentally conscious logistical processes (M=4.527). Moreover, the employees were in agreement that the total logistic cost is reduced by government subsidies. (M=4.427) and operating and maintaince cost of EVs are less than other vehicles (M=4.527). The workers also agree that acquisition cost of EVs is high and repairs and maintaince is less. The respondents also agreed that the use of EVs has positive impact logistic operations (M=4.111) and they also agreed that they gain the depreciation benefits (M=4.694) and the subsidies provided by reduction in logistical operating cost (M=4.417) due to government regulation of EV use. The view of respondents is statistically significant. Hence null hypothesis H0 – “The usage of EVs in logistic operations are not minimizing the logistic cost” is rejected and alternative hypothesis H1 – “The usage of EVs in logistic operations are minimizing the logistic cost” is accepted.

7.2 Perception of logistic workers regarding impact of EVs on environmental sustainability.

One of the primary purpose of adopting EVs in logistic operations at manufacturing industries is to eliminates the carbon footprints. This also creates the way for promoting green operations, which in turn impact on environmental sustainability. Hence some of the questionnaires has developed to get the information on perception of logistic workers regarding impact of EVs on environmental sustainability. This sections of paper runs through descriptive analysis in the view of logistic workers regarding impact of EVs on environmental sustainability.

Table No.4 Results of one sample T-test relating to perception of logistic workers (Inventory managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) regarding impact of EVs on environmental sustainability.

Perception variable regarding the impact of EVs	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Sig
On environmental sustainability					
1.The carbon emission can be reduced dueTo usage of EVs in logistic operation.	37	4.211	1.258	5.922	0.00
2.The use of EVs is positively impacting onNatural environment.	37	4.694	0.624	16.286	0.00
3.The import of fossil fuel can be Minimized by adopting EVs in logistic operation.	37	4.455	0.696	12.683	0.00
4.The use of EVs minimizes the Exploitation of non renewable energy.	37	4.250	0.125	5.977	0.00
5.The use of EVs helps in preserving nonRenewable energy for future generation.	37	4.472	0.734	12.703	0.00

Source: Primary data

Table No.4 shows the results of one sample T-test relating to perception of logistic workers (Inventory

managers, Warehouse managers, Logistic network managers) regarding impact of EVs on environmental sustainability, which indicates all variables shows p-value less than 0.05. The logistic workers are in agreement that using electric vehicles in logistic operations may cut carbon emissions (M=4.211) and have a beneficial influence on the environment (M=4.694). They also agreed that the import of fossil fuels can be minimized by adopting EVs in logistic operation (M=4.455) and the usage of EVs limits the abuse of non environmentally friendly power (M=4.25), which can also be preserved for future generation (M=4.472). The view of respondents is statistically significant. Hence null hypothesis H₀ –“The EVs in logistic operations are not significantly contributing to environmental sustainability” is rejected and alternative hypothesis H₁ –“ The EVs in logistic operations are significantly contributing to environmental sustainability” is accepted.

8. Conclusion:

Today we can observe that most of the people are adopting EVs for their transportation purpose which will reduce the usage of other alternative fuel vehicles. In such a manner making business is fundamental organization to adopt the EVs in logistic operations which will reduce the usage of other alternative fuel vehicles and also reduces the logistic cost and this will largely impact on sustainable environment. Descriptive and inferential statistics showed that using EVs in logistics operations has a major effect on logistic cost and may have a major effect on environmental sustainability. In conclusion, the research determined that there are several advantages to using EVs in logistic operations for manufacturing concern. These include reduced logistic costs, increased subsidies, low carbon emissions, and a positive impact on environmental sustainability.

The current research shows that in order to reap advantages for both the company and the environment, it is essential to always be on the lookout for innovative methods and approaches to corporate operations. High fuel costs, a big pollution footprint, and greater environmental taxes are just a few of the logistical hurdles that EVs will remove. Therefore, EVs will be primary source for any of the manufacturing concern for its operation which simplifies manufacturing process, minimize logistic cost, improving profitability and contributing towards sustainable environment.

9. Limitation of study:

This research is also not an exception. Its shortcomings included an exclusive emphasis on logistical costs and environmental sustainability, as well as a failure to address other factors, such as the difficulties associated with EV adoption, charging infrastructure, and preservation. In addition, the research's methodology had its own limitations, which might have an impact on the findings, and the study just looked at the perspectives of logistic professionals (i.e., warehouse managers, logistic network managers) without considering other specialists.

10. Scope for future research:

Research in the future may concentrate on developing robust theoretical models that might advise companies on how to incorporate electric vehicles into their current business strategies while simultaneously increasing their positive impact on the environment and bringing them closer to the UN's Sustainable Development Goals.

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